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3.Unlocking a Growth Mindset for Personal and Professional Potential through Corporate Social Responsibility

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Introduction-Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) refers to the efforts companies make to address social, environmental, and economic issues in a responsible manner. It's about going beyond profit-making to impact society and the environment positively. Carol Dweck is a psychologist who developed the growth mindset theory. She popularized the concept in her book Mindset: The New Psychology of Success. Her research has influenced educational practices, and many schools have adopted her ideas. The idea that our intelligence can be developed is a major factor in success. A growth mindset is a theory that suggests that our minds can improve over time, especially with effort. Some people are naturally more orderly and achievement-oriented, while others are born with unusual talents. While these traits are not equally distributed. According to Stanford psychologist Carol Dweck, "human beings have the potential to learn and develop new skills and abilities, no matter what their starting point is." A growth mindset is a theory that encourages people to think bigger than they already are and take on new challenges. This mindset can help people thrive even in the toughest of times. In addition, it has been associated with many positive outcomes, including increased health and productivity. Teachers can adopt growth mindset instruction by encouraging students to take responsibility for their own learning. They can also encourage students to seek help and use resources. In addition to this, a growth mindset helps teachers normalize struggle, which encourages students to approach challenges in a positive way. This helps them to engage with challenges, rather than dismiss them in a boring and uninteresting way.

Role of CSR for Growth Mindset in the Present Era-Education has a very important role to play in the development paradigm of any country. The combination of CSR and Growth Mindset creates a powerful synergy that drives positive changes and sustainable development for society as well as educational institutions. CSR initiatives support both the students and educators. For empowering students and educators, different types of workshops are organized for their personal and professional development. Growth Mindset motivates educators to improve their teaching strategies through professional development and mentorship programs, and conduct awareness campaigns for students to raise awareness about the importance of education and skill development. When we dive deeper

into how these two concepts complement each other we find CSR and Growth Mindset are equally contributing to fostering innovation and creativity, funding educational programs, providing scholarships and grants to the underprivileged, investing in infrastructure development, technical institutes to offer vocational training programs that equip students with practical skills, hand-on experiences through apprenticeships and internships, implementation of online learning platforms to make education more accessible, enhancing digital literacy and technology integration, and building stronger communities. For example, IBM's P-TECH Program, Infosys Foundation, Intel AI for Youth Program, etc.

Key Strategies to Cultivate and Maintain a Growth Mindset-Unlocking a growth mindset is a powerful approach to personal and professional potential. Here are some key strategies to cultivate and maintain a growth mindset:**Embracing Challenges**-Educators should view challenges or problems as an opportunity to learn and resolve the obstacles and inculcate the same in their pupils. Educators can develop resilience in pupils and enhance their ability to bounce back from failures.**Focus on Learning & Learning from Criticism**-Educators and pupils should cultivate curiosity and a desire to explore new things, ideas, and concepts. If they are committed to lifelong or continuous learning and seeking out new knowledge and skills, it will cultivate a growth mindset. It is important for both the Educator and the Pupils to accept constructive feedback as a valuable tool for improvement in their existing flaws. If they regularly reflect on their performances and identify their strengths and weaknesses, then they can make a positive change in their personal and professional potential. **Setting Realistic Goals**-Educators and students should follow incremental progress in order to break down larger goals into small and manageable steps. SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound) goals should be set by the organization, Educators, and Pupils that will help in achieving goals and reaching their full potential. **Practicing Self-Compassion & Self-Efficacy**-Educators and Pupils need to treat themselves with kindness and understanding, especially when an adverse situation occurs. It is important to learn from past mistakes and view mistakes as learning opportunities rather than failures.**Embracing Change**-To embrace the change, two major strategies should be adopted. First is adaptability, and second is flexibility. Educators and pupils should be open to change and willing to adapt to new circumstances and develop flexibility in thinking and problem-solving approaches.

Integrating Personal and Professional Potential with SDG4 (Quality Education)In addition to promoting possibilities for lifelong learning, SDG4 seeks to ensure inclusive, equitable, and high-quality education. The

Sustainable Development Goals Report (2023) states that it is becoming increasingly difficult for the globe to attain high-quality education. Although the rate of completion of primary and secondary school is increasing, it is happening slowly and unevenly. The study concluded that, in the absence of further action, just one in six nations will meet universal secondary school completion goals by 2030, 84 million children and teenagers will not be enrolled in school, and 300 million kids will lack basic literacy and numeracy abilities. Integrating professional and personal development with SDG4 is a powerful strategy for ensuring that everyone has access to high-quality and inclusive education. Said & Abdullah (2024) explored lifelong learning for sustainable development, aligning adult education with Sustainable Development Goal4. The paper underscores the need for workplace-based lifelong learning programs that incorporate andragogical ideas to tackle organizational sustainability concerns. These programs enable adult employees to enhance their comprehension of sustainability principles, promote sustainable behaviors, and facilitate positive workplace transformation. Personal development with SDG4 encourages individuals to continue learning, which helps them to adapt to their environments and encourages them to acquire new skills. Personal development programs emphasize problem-solving skills and critical thinking. These programs enable them to navigate composite challenges, and they will contribute to sustainable development. Professional development is decisive for educators, and it is crucial for the improved quality of education. The training programs equip educators with the latest technological skills and pedagogical techniques. Workplace-based learning programs are aligned with SDG4, which is promoted by sustainable practices that allow the development of desired skills. SDG4 ensures inclusive education and global partnership. Personal and professional development programs could support this by addressing the hurdles in the educational field and encouraging inclusivity.

Challenges in Unlocking a Growth Mindset for Personal and Professional Potential-Unlocking a growth mindset is a continuous process that requires continuous reflection and corrective measures because, in this process, many challenges can be faced. Unlocking a growth mindset is incredibly beneficial in the field of education, but it comes with a set of challenges for both personal and professional potential. Here are some common challenges that create hurdles in unlocking a growth mindset for personal and professional potential.

Personal Potential Challenges- •People are afraid of adopting a growth mindset because of their fear of failure. So, they don't want to try new things beyond their boundaries. Even if they are willing but their fear of failure creates a hurdle in accepting a growth mindset. •Fixed

mindset habits of people give up easily because those with a fixed mindset believe that talents are an innate gift and not easily changed. Their preconception about themselves doesn't motivate them to try something new. •People who lack self-confidence and self-belief face a significant hindrance in their growth because they doubt their own actions. This is the fundamental aspect of a growth mindset. Believing in its own actions and abilities is the first step of a growth mindset. •Comfort zone refers to a psychological state in which we feel safe and do not experience anxiety or fear. Stepping out of one's comfort zone is important for personal growth. People are feeling uncomfortable leaving their comfort zone, which makes hindrance in their growth mindset. •People don't focus on their personal growth and comparing themselves with others, which creates a feeling of inadequacy. They aren't satisfied with their growth, which creates hindrances to their growth mindset

Professional Potential Challenges•Sometimes the workplace culture may not support a growth mindset. Workplace culture is the shared values, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors that define an organization's work environment. A positive culture can make employees more engaged and satisfied. •Professional development needs adequate resources such as human resources, financial resources, physical resources, and information resources. Limited resources create hindrances in the growth of an organization. All the resources need to be used properly for growth. •Resistance to change is the reluctance of people or organizations to adopt new ideas, processes, or behavior. In a professional setting, people resist change. Embracing new ways of thinking and working can be challenging. •Organizations that focus on short-term results and do not have a long-term vision cannot grow. This can discourage the employees in their growth and development, and ultimately the organization's growth. •Constructive feedback is a form of communication that aims to help someone improve by providing helpful comments and suggestions. Therefore, constructive feedback is essential for growth, but developing a positive attitude towards feedback is crucial. By recognizing and addressing these challenges, like cultivating self-awareness, embracing failure, seeking feedback, and setting realistic goals, individuals and organizations may foster continuous growth and development.

Impact of Personal and Professional Development with Quality Education for Vision Vikshit Bharat @ 2047-The 'Vikshit Bharat @ 2047' agenda is a comprehensive vision plan by the Government of India, aiming to transform India into a developed nation by the year 2047, marking the 100th anniversary of its independence. For the realization of Vikshit Bharat, SDG4 (Quality Education) plays a decisive role in achieving this vision. •To ensure high-quality education, more investment is needed for the

educational infrastructure, teacher training, and updating the curriculum to the current needs. Encourage inclusivity so that all students, regardless of their background, have access to quality education. It will encourage social equity and reduce disparities, which has a great importance for the vision Vikshit Bharat. •For the realization of Vikshit Bharat, it is important to focus on personal and professional development with quality education. By fostering continuous and lifelong learning, educators and pupils can develop their skills, which is important to survive in this competitive job market. It becomes important to stay active and adapt to new technological advancements, and contribute to the economic growth of the nation. Different types of training programs and professional growth programs ensure that employees are equipped with the latest skills and innovations. •By educating the pupils about sustainable practices and environmental conservation, it will result in an environment-conscious society. Community services can be taught through different personal and professional programs. It will promote a sense of responsibility towards society. •The government initiatives to align with the goals of Vikshit Bharat, focusing on skill India initiatives that provide vocational training and skill development to the youth of the nation. The Digital India campaign is a flagship program of the Government of India launched on July 1, 2015, with the vision to transform India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy.

Conclusion-Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) plays a significant role in fostering a growth mindset within the educational field. Education is a key driver of socio-economic development. CSR initiatives can bridge the educational gaps by providing essential resources. A growth mindset encourages embracing challenges and learning from failures. A growth mindset can drive continuous improvement and innovations in CSR practices, making businesses more resilient, adaptive, and positively impactful on society. By leveraging CSR initiatives and integrating a growth mindset, organizations can contribute significantly to building a skilled workforce that is ready to meet the challenges of the future. This paper not only benefits the community but also helps organizations create a sustainable and socially responsible environment. The government is playing an important role in CSR and in promoting a growth mindset within society. The government sets the regulations and legislation, promotes awareness, and implements educational reforms that emphasize critical thinking, problem-solving, and lifelong learning, which can unlock a growth mindset in students from an early age.

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4. Central Bank Digital Currencies (CBDCs) on Financial Inclusion: A Comparative Assessment of Sand Dollar and eNaira

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Introduction-Financial inclusion is a critical aspect of inclusive economic development and social equity. It refers to the process of ensuring access to appropriate, affordable, and timely financial products and services for all individuals and businesses, especially the underserved and unbanked segments of society. These services include savings accounts, credit, insurance, pensions, and digital payments. The ultimate goal is to empower people by offering them tools to improve their financial well-being, reduce poverty, and promote economic stability. As economies become more digital and interconnected, financial inclusion has gained increased attention from policymakers, financial institutions, and international organizations. It is now seen as not only a moral imperative but also a strategic approach to sustainable development. The World Bank defines financial inclusion as "individuals and businesses having access to useful and affordable financial products and services that meet their needs—transactions, payments, savings, credit, and insurance—delivered in a responsible and sustainable way."

Financial inclusion focuses on four main dimensions:
1. Access – The ability to use financial services.
2. Usage – The regularity and frequency with which financial services are used.
3. Quality – The relevance, affordability, and suitability of the services.
4. Impact – The positive effects of financial access on individuals' and businesses' lives. Significant progress has been made globally in recent years. According to the World Bank's Global Findex Database 2021:(1).76% of adults worldwide now have an account with a bank or regulated institution, up from 51% in 2011.(2).In developing economies, account ownership rose from 63% in 2017 to 71% in 2021.(3).Digital payments have become a major driver of inclusion. About 40% of adults in developing economies made a digital merchant payment in 2021.

Central Bank Digital Currencies (CBDCs)-Central Bank Digital Currencies (CBDCs) are digital versions of a country's fiat currency issued and backed by its central bank. Unlike cryptocurrencies, they are legal tender and regulated by the government. Fiat money is a currency that is issued by government which has no physical commodity such as gold or silver. It is a type of currency which can be exchanged for goods and services. Talking about earlier years, fiat money was coins and bank notes but with the advent of the technology, it allowed the government and